

TABLE-1

Compound	m.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analytical (%)						UV Absorption spectra λ_{max} in nm
				Calcd.			Found			
				C	H	N	C	H	N	
I, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₀	265-66	72	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	62.74	8.50	18.80	62.40	8.44	17.99	924
II, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₀	264-65	69	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	63.75	8.75	17.50	63.90	8.58	17.19	924
III, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₀	266-67	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	65.50	9.19	16.09	65.22	9.27	15.85	929
IV, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₀	263-65	76	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	67.03	9.60	14.90	66.75	9.65	14.73	925
V, R=C ₁₁ H ₁₀	261-64	74	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	68.31	9.90	13.86	68.40	9.69	13.58	923

200, 100, 50 and 12.5 mg/kg body weight and maximum survivality was shown by V at 400 mg dose level, the T/C was 114% whereas T/C $\leq$ 125% was considered active⁶.

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Chemical Investigation of the Stem Bark of *Canthium dicoccum*

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THE isolation of α -amyrin and oleanolic acid¹ and a new triterpene acid called canthic acid² from the stem bark of *C. dicoccum* Gaertn. Merr. (Syn. *C. didymum* Gaertn.) was reported earlier. The present communication reports the isolation of two coumarins, aesculetin dimethyl ether and scopoletin, and a triterpene acid sapogenin, acetyl ursolic acid from the same source.

The ethanolic extract of air-dried powdered defatted stem bark of *C. dicoccum* was concentrated and excess of diethyl ether was added to precipitate the crude glycosides. The ether layer was decanted off. Two compounds, compound-A and compound-B, were isolated from the ether soluble part by preparative tlc over silica gel G. The crude glycoside obtained from the ether insoluble part was hydrolysed with acid and the aglycone part was separated into acid and neutral parts. The acid part on column chromatography over silica gel gave compound-C.

Compound-A, C₁₁H₁₀O₄ (M⁺206), m.p. 145° [λ_{max} (EtOH): 229, 251, 257, 293 and 344 nm (log ϵ 4.27, 3.77, 3.68, 3.75 and 4.03 respectively). ν_{max} (Nujol mull): 1720 cm⁻¹ (coumarin lactone ring). ¹H NMR spectrum: (90 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 6.23 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-3), 7.58 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-4), 3.90 (6H, s, 2 x-OCH₃), 6.83 (1H, s) and 6.80 (1H, s) for H-5 and H-8. Mass spectrum: m/e 206, 191, 178, 163, 135 and 120] appeared to be 6,7-dimethoxy coumarin (aesculetin dimethyl ether)³ which was finally characterised by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and ir spectra).

Compound-B, C₁₀H₈O₄ (M⁺192), m.p. 204° [λ_{max} (EtOH): 230, 254, 260, 298 and 346 nm. (log ϵ 4.10, 3.65, 3.60, 3.65 and 4.07 respectively). ν_{max} (Nujol mull): 1706 cm⁻¹ (coumarin lactone ring) and 3360 cm⁻¹ (phenolic-OH). ¹H NMR spectrum: (80 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 6.25 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-3), 7.57 (1H, d, J=9.5 Hz, H-4), 6.20 (1H, s, phenolic -OH, partially merged with the doublet centred at δ 6.25, disappeared on D₂O exchange), 3.95 (3H, s -OCH₃), 6.89 (1H, s) and 6.82 (1H, s) for H-5 and H-8. Mass spectrum: m/e 192, 177, 164, 149 and 121] appeared to be 6-methoxy, 7-hydroxy coumarin (scopoletin)⁴ which was finally characterised by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and ir spectra).

Compound-C, C₂₃H₃₀O₄, m.p. 286-87°, formed a monomethyl ester, C₂₃H₃₂O₄ (M⁺512), m.p. 243-44°. It gave pink $\rightarrow$ violet colouration in Liebermann-Buchard test and a pale yellow colouration in tetranitromethane test. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra of compound-C and mass spectrum of its monomethyl ester indicated the compound-C to be acetyl ursolic acid⁵ which was finally characterised by direct comparison with an

authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and ir spectra).

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Chemical Examination of Three Indigenous Plants

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CANTHIUM *didymum* Roxb.¹ (Syn. *C. dicoccum* Gaertn.) (Rubiaceae) is a low branched evergreen tree distributed in many parts of India. A survey of literature revealed that no chemical work has been done on the leaf of this plant though the bark has been examined by different workers²⁻⁵.

Air dried powdered leaves (460 g) collected from Mayurbhanj Dist., Orissa were exhaustively extracted with rectified spirit. The alcoholic extract was divided into ether soluble and ether insoluble parts. Ether soluble part was separated into acid and neutral fractions by extraction with aqueous NaOH (10%). Chromatography of the acid fraction over silica gel yielded two pure compounds A and B. Compound-A (21 mg) was crystallised from CHCl₃-pet. ether; m.p. 145-146°. It showed bright blue fluorescence in uv light and gave positive test for coumarin. UV (EtOH): 227, 251, 296, 346; ir: 1710, 1600 cm⁻¹. It was identified as aesculetin dimethyl ether by comparison with an authentic sample (m. m. p., tlc, superimposable ir).

Compound-B was crystallised from CHCl₃-pet. ether, (6 mg); m. p. 203-204°. It responded to colour test for coumarin and showed blue fluorescence in uv light. UV (EtOH): 229, 252, 299, 344. It was identified as scopoletin by comparison with authentic compound (m. m. p., tlc).

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over alumina. Pet. ether-benzene (7:3) eluted fraction (40 mg) furnished fine needles (ethanol); m. p. 209-10°, [α]_D⁺²¹ (CHCl₃). The compound gave positive Liebermann-Buchard test and TNM colour reaction for an unsaturated triterpene. It exhibited no characteristic uv absorption above 220 nm and showed ir peaks at 3600, 1368, 1365, 875 cm⁻¹. It gave an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°) crystallised in needles (CHCl₃-pet. ether); m. p. 216-217°, [α]_D⁺⁴⁸ (CHCl₃). It was identified as lupeol by comparison with authentic specimen (m. m. p., tlc, ir).

The pet. ether-benzene (1:9) eluates afforded fine flakes (19 mg); m. p. 136-137°. It gave pink-violet-blue-green colour with L-B reagent and yielded an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°); m.p. 127-128°, identical (m. m. p., tlc, ir) with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate.

Pithecellobium saman Benth. (Syn. *Samanea saman* Merril.) (Mimosaceae) is a large tree popularly known as raintree. The bark and leaves of this plant have been examined chemically⁶⁻⁹. The pods were reported¹⁰⁻¹² to contain lupeol, α -spinasterol, α -spinasterol- β -D-glucoside, palmitic acid, stearic acid, acacic acid and mixtures of flavonoids. Our re-investigation of the pods resulted in the isolation of echinocystic acid and acacic acid lactone not reported earlier along with lupeol and α -spinasterol.

The air-dried powdered pods (6.8 g) of *P. saman* collected locally was Soxhleted with alcohol for 62 hr. The ether insoluble part of this alcoholic extract was hydrolysed with 3% alcoholic H₂SO₄ and worked up in the usual manner. The sapogenins thus obtained were separated into acid and neutral fractions.

The neutral part, on repeated chromatography over alumina, yielded acacic acid lactone (20 mg) crystallised from ethanol as needles; m.p. 253-255°, ir: 3400, 1760, 1371, 970 cm⁻¹. It gave an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°) crystallised as colourless small needles; m. p. 233-235°. The identity of the compound was established by direct comparison with authentic specimen (m. m. p., tlc, ir). The acid fraction was esterified and chromatographed over alumina. Benzene-CHCl₃ (1:1) eluted a pure compound crystallised from ethanol; m. p. 210-211°, ir: 3500, 1700, 1370 cm⁻¹. It afforded an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°); m. p. 200-203°. Finally, the methyl ester and its acetate was identified as methyl echinocystate and diacetate methyl echinocystate by comparison with authentic specimen (m. m. p., tlc, ir).

The ether soluble part, on chromatography over alumina, yielded lupeol; m.p. 209-210°; ir: 3400, 1639, 882 cm⁻¹, acetate m.p. 211-212°, identified as